

CLEAN SKY 2 TECHNOLOGY EVALUATOR

N. Flüthmann¹, A. Junior¹, A. Leipold¹, W. Grimme¹, M. Gelhausen¹, T. Zill²

¹German Aerospace Center, Linder Höhe, Cologne (Germany), Email: nico.fluethmann@dlr.de

²German Aerospace Center, Hein-Saß-Weg 22, Hamburg (Germany)

KEYWORDS: Aviation Technology, Sustainable Aviation Fuels, Clean Sky, Assessment, Scenarios, Environment, Technology Evaluator

ABSTRACT: Clean Sky 2 is a European aeronautics program in form of a Public Private Partnership as cooperation of all important European actors from industry and research. Large Technology Demonstrator Platforms cover the whole aeronautical spectrum from fast rotorcrafts, business jets, and small air transport up to regional and mainliner aircraft with the objective to test and validate innovative technologies to be integrated into future aircraft.

Cross-positioned within the Clean Sky 2 programme, the Technology Evaluator is a dedicated evaluation platform. It has the key role of assessing the environmental impact of those technologies and their level of success towards the Clean Sky 2 environmental objectives on CO₂, NO_x and noise. An additional focus is on societal benefits.

Global forecasts for the relevant Clean Sky 2 vehicle types until 2035 represent the central basis for the TE impact assessment. In order to be able to make further statements about the possible future passenger and fleet development of the considered vehicle types in the period 2035 - 2050, it was also necessary to develop vehicle-specific scenarios in addition to the generated forecasts. The general scenario development process is the second main part of this paper and the corresponding conference presentation.

1. CLEAN SKY 2

Following the agenda of the Clean Sky programme (2008-2017), in 2014 the Clean Sky 2 programme ambitiously continued the successful research collaboration between partners from European industry and research. The participants have

defined a set of goals to make a considerable contribution towards more sustainable air transport operations based on multidisciplinary research, intense aerospace industry collaboration and a long-term perspective. Researching and testing technological innovations and aircraft improvements play a central role by enabling the implementation of the European Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) for aviation and the corresponding 'Flightpath 2050' goals [1].

2. TECHNOLOGY EVALUATOR

The Technology Evaluator is Clean Sky's instrument for critical self-reflection, assessing the expected environmental, societal and economic benefits of technology advancements being developed in Clean Sky 2 and the related longer-term impact on the air transport system.

The focus is on meeting Clean Sky's self-imposed emissions and noise reduction goals, improving mobility and connectivity in Europe as well as strengthening the competitiveness of the European aviation sector.

The technology impact assessments in Clean Sky 2 cover environmental and socio-economic impacts with a particular focus on reducing CO₂, NO_x and noise emissions by 20-30% relative to a "state-of-the-art" aircraft which entered into service in 2014. Where applicable, benefits of Clean Sky 2 demonstrators and technologies will be monitored against well-defined environmental targets and socio-economic targets of the ACARE Flightpath 2050 and the corresponding goals outlined in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) [2].

Clean Sky 2 technologies will generally be considered in the form of "concept aircraft models" and related impacts will be assessed on three levels. The levels and the assessment categories

are “Mission Level”, “Airport Level” and “Air Transport System Level” [2].

Figure 1: Metrics, Levels, Dimensions of the Clean Sky Technology Evaluator

At "Mission Level" (micro level) the environmental and the socio-economic assessment dimension will be covered. In respect of the environmental assessment dimension, the future concept aircraft models and their respective reference aircraft counterparts which relate to aircraft having entered the market in 2014 will be compared for single representative missions to determine the environmental benefit of the Clean Sky 2 technologies. Criteria will be oriented around noise on the ground (measured in dB levels), as well as CO₂ and NO_x emissions. Also planned is consideration of SO_x, VOC and particles to complete the focus on climate impact analyses. In terms of the socio-economic dimension, the Technology Evaluator will cover mobility and connectivity impacts at mission level up to a certain extent by determining rotorcraft mission productivity improvements (e.g. travel time savings through higher cruise speed). Life cycle assessments of the socio-economic impact at single aircraft level will be performed by Eco-Design and mark a separate assessment approach at a different level of granularity and with a different focus. For the Technology Evaluator assessment tasks, the mission level assessment horizon is benchmarked against year 2014 and the future assessment years 2025, 2035 and 2050.

At "Airport Level" (meso level), Clean Sky 2 concept aircraft insertion modelling into the global fleet is used to derive airport fleet traffic scenarios. In parallel to mission level, this will be carried out for the future assessment years 2025, 2035 and 2050 to provide a basis for comparison to the reference year 2014. The focus of the planned assessments in the environmental dimension will concentrate on CO₂, NO_x and noise on the ground (measured in dB levels). As the focus on airport level affects local traffic distribution, the share of population affected by aircraft noise can additionally be estimated. If technically and methodologically feasible, the assessment at airport level will additionally cover SO_x, H₂O, VOC, particles and local air quality to complete the environmental impact evaluation. For the socio-economic assessments the analysis at airport level will concentrate on mobility improvements expected for the assessment years 2025, 2045 and 2050 in comparison to the reference year 2014. Connectivity improvements, travel time savings and benefits for “remote” regions will be evaluated at airport level. Besides this airport-centered analysis, the socio-economic impact assessment at meso level is planned to also consider competitiveness assessments. These will focus on the benefits that are generated through the Clean Sky 2 programme. Due to the diversity of the topic, these assessments will be done in the form of status-quo analyses as the starting point for identifying future trends but with no particular linkage to the specific assessment years [2].

At "Air Transport System Level", Clean Sky 2 concept aircraft insertion into the global fleet is modelled to obtain worldwide fleet traffic forecasts and scenarios. Corresponding to mission and airport level, this will be done for the assessment years 2025, 2035 and 2050. The environmental impact analysis will in this respect cover CO₂ and NO_x emissions. Again, if technically and methodologically feasible, SO_x, H₂O, VOC and particles will be considered to estimate the global warming potential aggregated at world fleet level. The socio-economic impact analysis will be focused around the same assessment horizon and estimate the GDP and employment impact at national and global scale. In parallel to the competitiveness assessment foreseen for meso

level, the plan is to have a corresponding assessment at the macro level by investigating the overall employment effects and looking at job creation in research and technological development relating to the Clean Sky 2 programme. To produce feasible results, this specific assessment will again concentrate on status-quo analyses at the point in time when it is conducted [2].

The technology assessment steps for the three different levels will be based on all concept aircraft considered in Clean Sky 2, including mainliners, regional aircraft, business jets, small air transport vehicles, fast rotorcraft, as well as on specific Technology Evaluator concept aircraft models. The latter provide the potential to integrate further Clean Sky 2 technologies. As these technologies are developed in the form of single components (e.g. a specific engine developed by an engine manufacturer) and not foreseen to be implemented in an aircraft model by the other Clean Sky 2 partners in form of a full demonstrator, this approach allows the Technology Evaluator to assess their impact in parallel to the three assessment dimensions [2].

3. SCENARIOS 2035 - 2050

As already mentioned in the abstract global forecasts for the relevant Clean Sky 2 vehicle types until 2035 represent the central basis for the TE impact assessments. In order to be able to make further statements about the possible future passenger and fleet development of the considered vehicle types in the time period 2035 - 2050, it was also necessary to develop vehicle-specific scenarios in addition to the generated forecasts. The general scenario development process will be described in the following chapters.

3.1 Factors identification and analysis

For the development of the scenarios, a comprehensive influencing factor analysis was first carried out, which aimed to identify any fields and factors that could influence future aviation development. For this purpose, a large number of scenario publications were analyzed, which have a thematically focus on aviation, are not older than 20 years and include scenarios with a time horizon

of at least until the year 2030. In addition to concrete air traffic scenario publications, also scenario studies with a thematic focus on the fields of "Transport, Mobility, Logistics", "Economy" or "Environment, Energy" were analyzed because they are closely linked to aviation. By means of further DLR internal expert interviews a comprehensive collection of relevant factors that have to be considered in the development of air traffic scenarios could be created.

In order to structure the extensive collection of relevant influencing factors on the future aviation development and to create an adequate taxonomy for the scenarios, a "STEEP" categorization approach was chosen. All identified influencing factors are assigned to the five overarching key fields Society, Technology, Economy, Environment and Policies. The key field Technology was further divided into transport-related technology and non-transport-related technology.

Figure 2: STEEP-A categorization structure

Also in the key field Policies a corresponding further separation into the subsections aviation-related and institutional & social-political frameworks was made. Finally, the STEEP categorization key fields have been expanded by the key fields Aviation Technology and Aviation Market Development, which are central for the definition of the vehicle specific aviation scenarios. Table 1 provides an overview of the central influencing factors from the key fields Aviation Technology and Aviation Market Development. In the course of the scenario development it was necessary to create scenario-specific and vehicle

type specific assumptions for each of these influencing factors.

Key Field	Factor
Aviation Technology	Sustainable Aviation Jet Fuels (SAJF)
	Electrical Propulsion
	Hydrogen
	Fuel Consumption/ Efficiency
	New Aircraft Types
	Aircraft System Technology
	Maintenance Technology
	Improvement Technologies (Propulsion, Noise etc.)
Aviation Market Development	Air Traffic Management
	Supply
	Demand
	Competition in Aviation Industry / between Airlines
	Business Models
	Network Connectivity
	Competition with other modes of transport

Table 1: Aviation-internal influencing factors for the vehicle specific scenario differentiation

The developed scenarios (high: great technological progress + number of flights; low: low technological progress + number of flights) for each vehicle type had to meet certain conditions regarding consistency and plausibility. On the one hand, it was important to make internally consistent and plausible assumptions that do not conflict with the technological assumptions and market-related assumptions of the respective vehicle type. On the other hand, consistency and plausibility to the external conditions had to be guaranteed. Thus, the vehicle-specific aviation scenarios (high + low) had to be “within the bounds of possibility”.

3.2 Taxonomy development and scenario structure

Based on the influencing factors identification and categorization, an appropriate scenario taxonomy was finally developed. As mentioned in chapter 3.1, the aviation scenarios should meet four key requirements:

- Period of time: 2035 – 2050
- Two scenarios (high + low) for every Clean Sky 2 vehicle type (Mainliner, Regional Aircraft, Business Jet, Small Air Transport, Rotorcraft)
- Scenario differentiation only based on aviation internal influencing factors
- No differentiation of the external framework developments

Based on these requirements and the results of chapter 3.1, the structure of the taxonomy can be derived, which is shown in Table 2. Accordingly, all influencing factors from the fields of aviation technology and aviation market development (see chapter 3.1) must be defined and described separately for each vehicle type and for each of the two scenarios (high + low). Based solely on these two key fields, the primary scenario differentiation is made. These assumptions were made based on specific literature review, CS 2 manufacturers input as well as DLR internal technology survey input.

Key field	Vehicle-specific	Scenario-specific	Constant assumptions*
Aviation Technology	•	•	
Aviation Market Development	•	•	
Society			•
Technology I Non-transport-related			•
Technology II Transport-related			•
Economy			•
Environment			•
Policies I Aviation-related			•
Policies II Institutional & socio-political frameworks			•

Table 2: Scenario taxonomy, *partly some differentiations to justify vehicle specific scenario differentiations

The central external framework developments, in particular quantitative assumptions such as GDP or world population, are not varied in the two scenarios. Although slight differentiations are indispensable in some areas, especially with regard to technology and energy-related assumptions, in order to justify the aviation-specific and scenario-specific developments. In general, however, the external framework developments in both scenarios should be kept as similar as possible.

3.3 Framework Development descriptions

Following the identification of all relevant influencing factors on the long-term air traffic development and the explanation of the general scenario taxonomy, the central framework developments which are underlying for both scenarios will be explained. These can be subdivided into the key fields Society, Technology, Economics, Environment and Politics, and in turn comprise various factors. As can be seen already

in the taxonomy in chapter 3.2, the same framework development assumptions has to be defined for both scenarios, which are all based on the most probable future development of the individual key fields and factors. Thus, the scenario differentiation has to be made exclusively by differentiating assumptions in aviation internal key fields (technology & market). This will provide an adequate basis for assessing the success and impact of new aviation technologies and aviation markets. All other key fields with impact on the future aviation development are not differentiated in terms of their basic assumptions. Exceptions are individual (energy) technological assumptions in order to be able to plausibly justify the different advances of the aviation technology in the two scenarios. In the following the future development of the key field Society will be described. As already mentioned these assumptions will be the same for both Scenarios. (All other external Key Fields will be presented in course of the conference presentation)

For the future development of air traffic, the development of the society is of crucial importance. Thus, the demand characteristics of future passengers and the total potential size of the aviation passenger market are strongly influenced by social and demographic changes.

The world population will continue to grow until 2050. While 7.7 billion people live on Earth in 2019, by the middle of the century the global population will exceed 9.7 billion. However, the growth rate of the world population will continue to decline. While it was 2.1 percent per annum for the period 1965-1970 and 1.1 percent per year for 2015-2020, the annual growth rate in the period of time 2014-2050 will be 0.8 percent per year. However, global population growth until 2050 will be significantly different among world regions. Accordingly, the lion's share of this growth will be in countries of sub-Saharan Africa (52%) and Central / Southeast Asia (25%) [3]. Due to the continuing increase in average life expectancy in combination with decreasing fertility rates, there are significant changes in the age composition of the world population, which is also described by the term "population aging". Thus, the proportion of older people, especially in the current

industrialized countries, will increase strongly by the middle of the century. At global level, the numbers of over 65 year old people will more than double between 2019 and 2050 [3] [4]. In addition, increasing global economic and demographic asymmetries will lead to a further increase of international migration. Europe, North America and Oceania will continue to be the main destination regions and Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean will be the major origins of these migration flows. In this development, international migration can be seen as a balancing factor for labor markets in the countries of origin and destination and as a means of raising the standard of migrants' families, and thus can play an important role in addressing future global economic and social challenges [4] [5] [6].

Another megatrend that will shape global society in the coming decades is the increasing urbanization. Thus, in 2050, nearly 70 percent of the world's total population will live in urban areas; at a current rate of 55 percent. Thus, by the middle of the century, 2.5 billion more people will live in urban areas than they do today. The lion's share of this urban population growth (90 %) will be in Asia and Africa [7]. Another significant influence on future air traffic development has the development of the global middle class society. The increase of the share of people who are at least middle class, based on their disposable income, will also lead to an increase of the proportion of the global population with sufficient purchasing power for air travel.

	High	Low
Population Development	Increase of world population until 2100 but growth rate continues to fall	
World Population (in billion)	8.5 / 9.2 / 9.7 (2030 / 2040 / 2050)	
Population growth rates (p.a. in %, from 2014)	1.05 / 0.93 / 0.86 (2030 / 2040 / 2050)	
Social Trends	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Move towards more active and healthy lifestyles • Individualisation, more flexibility & acceleration of social life (<i>Liquid modernity</i>) • Experienced-based leisure (inter-cultural understanding, holidays etc.) • More free-time → Use for self-realisation; Focus on individual well-being • More environmental orientation • Emphasis on small-family size, material well-being, leisure • Increase of one-person / single-parent households + couples without children • Closing gender gaps; more connected societies 	
Mobility Patterns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility-as-a-Service & Sharing platforms replace private ownership • Less car use by younger generations • Convenient and flexible service and mobility • High requirements for physical & virtual mobility 	
Environmental Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase „Sustainable Consumption“ culture • Negative impacts of (air)transport on people are not accepted 	

Figure 3: Central scenario assumptions for the key field Society

By the year 2050, this proportion will continue to grow strongly in the world population, eventually reaching 66 percent by the middle of the century. Of particular importance for the future development of air traffic is the growth of the middle class society in Asia. Accordingly, aviation demand in the future will come especially from this region. By 2050, nearly 80 percent of global middle class consumption will come from Asia. China and India will make up the lion's share of this consumption, with a total of 55 percent [8] [9]. In addition to purely demographic and socio-economic factors, general changes in the value and behavior of global society in the future will have some influence on aviation development in the future. Over the next few decades, there will be a continued increase in the importance of more active and healthier lifestyles in global society. Also the drive for individualization and greater flexibility in global society will continue to grow. The increasing importance of more leisure time in society is being increasingly realized, among other things, by technological advances in automation, artificial intelligence or robotics. Leisure activities are increasingly used for self-realization. In addition, individual well-being will continue to be in the focus of the future society [10] [12]. Other social trends that will shape future society are an increased focus on smaller family sizes, a further increase in one-person households, the elimination of the "gender gap" and the stronger interconnection of society through digital technologies [5]. Also, the mobility behavior of the global society will change significantly in the coming decades. Accordingly, Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) approaches and sharing platforms will increasingly replace privately owned cars. In addition, the need for flexible and comfortable mobility in society will continue to increase in importance [10] [11].

The increasing importance of environmental awareness in the global society, which has risen enormously in 2019, especially through the "Greta Movement", will continue to increase until 2050. This will lead to an increasingly sustainable consumer culture in which any negative impact of traffic on society will not be accepted [10]. In addition to an already mentioned stronger interconnectedness of the global society, there will

be an increasing fragmentation of the society in the next decades, which is made possible by further advances of digital technologies as well as increasing globalization. Accordingly, the search for like-minded people on specific topics or political attitudes becomes more and more uncomplicated and thus the diversity of the global society or sub-societies becomes more and more visible.

3.4 Vehicle specific scenarios

After describing the external framework developments underlying the scenarios in chapter 3.3 (exemplary for the key field Society), this chapter now describes the individual vehicle-specific scenarios. Figure 4 shows the general, vehicle overarching, aviation-technological assumptions for the high scenario and the low scenario, which are described in more detail in the following chapter. It can be seen that advances in aviation technology are much more pronounced in the high scenario than in the low scenario. It should be mentioned that the individual technology factors vary significantly in terms of intensity or rather relevance for the respective vehicle types to be considered.

	High	Low
Sustainable Aviation Jet Fuels	High share	Medium share
Electrical propulsion	High share	Low share
Hydrogen	High share	Low share
Fuel consumption → Efficiency	Significant improvements	Medium/low improvements
New Aircraft Types	Yes	No, rather retrofits
Aircraft Systems Technology	Significant improvements	Medium/low improvements
Maintenance Technology	Significant improvements	Medium/low improvements
Air Traffic Management	Significant improvements	Medium/low improvements
Noise	Significant improvements	Medium/low improvements

Figure 4: General aviation internal technical assumptions for the vehicle specific scenarios

It should also be mentioned at this point that the scenario-specific technology assumptions presented in the following chapter generally represent possible developments and therefore, especially in the field of propulsion technologies (SAJF, electrics, hydrogen), primarily one technology will prevail for the respective vehicle types.

In the following section the high scenario and the low scenario for mainliners will be described. In the high scenario, the share of Sustainable Aviation Jet Fuels (as substitute for conventional kerosene) will increase from 10 percent in 2030 to 70 to 90 percent in 2050. In the low scenario, only a 30-50 percent SAJF share will be achieved in 2050. While in the low scenario neither all-electric nor hybrid-electric aircraft concepts will reach operational readiness, in the high scenario there will be an Entry-Into-Service in 2040 for hybrid-electric mainliners on short- and medium-haul routes and in 2050 even on long-haul routes. In addition, hydrogen-powered aircraft will be available in the high scenario from 2045 onwards. In the low scenario this technology plays no role for Mainliner.

Figure 5: Aviation Technology Scenario assumptions for Mainliner

On the one hand, the effects of the generally much larger share of "green" propulsion technologies in the high scenario are the significantly increased acceptance of air transport in society. In addition, the costs of emissions trading are significantly reduced. On the other hand, the development costs for such technologies are significantly higher than in the low scenario, in which the share of these alternative propulsion concepts is significantly lower.

Due to the large aircraft sizes and average longer flight distances of these types of vehicles, the overall relevance of SAJF for mainliners (in both scenarios) is significantly greater than electrified propulsion concepts.

A look at the fuel efficiency increase shows that these are significantly larger in the high scenario than in the low scenario and, accordingly, that the operational costs can be significantly reduced.

Figure 6: Aviation Technology + Aviation Market Development Scenario assumptions for Mainliner

In addition, aircraft technological noise reduction measures in the high scenario are much more successful, which in turn has a positive influence on the social acceptance of air traffic.

In addition to significant weight reductions in aircraft construction, new aircraft types are also being introduced in the high scenario. Thus, from the year 2045, market entries of blended wing body aircraft or "double bubble" aircraft concepts are possible. In the low scenario, only retrofits or upgrading of existing aircraft types will be realized. In the field of maintenance, in the high scenario, the increasing use of robotic and sensor technologies, self-diagnostic aircraft and predictive maintenance will lead to a significant increase in aircraft utilization.

As can be seen in Figure 5, in the high scenario, there will be much earlier Entry-Into-Services of technological components in the field of aircraft system technology than in the low scenario. In addition, sectorless air traffic management is introduced ten years earlier in the high scenario than in the low scenario.

4. CONCLUSION

The vehicle specific scenarios for the period 2035-2050 represent - additionally to the global forecasts for the relevant Clean Sky 2 vehicle types until 2035 - an important basis for the TE

Impact Assessments (especially in course of qualitative storylines as well as input parameters for the quantification of the scenarios). By this, two possible global market developments (high + low scenario) for each CS 2 vehicle type regarding number of flights, passengers and fleet until 2050 could be developed. This in turn is needed for assessing the environmental impact of innovative aviation technologies and their level of success towards the Clean Sky 2 environmental objectives on CO₂, NO_x and noise in course of the Technology Evaluator.

4. REFERENCES

1. DLR (2019): Clean Sky 2's Technology Evaluator: On target for sustainable air transport, <https://www.dlr.de/content/en/articles/aeronautics/clean-sky-2-technology-evaluator.html> [retrieved 16.12.2019]
2. Clean Sky (2019): Technology Evaluator, <https://www.cleansky.eu/technology-evaluator> [retrieved 16.12.2019]
3. United Nations [UN] (2019): World Population Prospects 2019. New York
4. United Nations [UN] (2017): World Population Prospects - The 2017 Revision. New York
5. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD] (2016): OECD Science, Technology and Innovation Outlook 2016. Paris
6. O'Neil, B. et. al. (2017) The roads ahead: Narratives for shared socioeconomic pathways describing world futures in the 21st century. In: Global Environmental Change, Volume 42, 2017, p. 169-180.
7. United Nations [UN] (2018): World Urbanization Prospects - The 2018 Revision. New York
8. Futures Centre (2016): The growing Middle Class, <https://thefuturescentre.org/printpdf/140> [retrieved 16.12.2019]
9. Futures Platform (2017): Global Middle-Class Grew Faster Than Expected <https://www.futuresplatform.com/blog/global-middle-class-grew-faster-expected>, [retrieved 16.12.2019]
10. Institute for Global Environmental Strategies [IGES] (2019): Society and Lifestyles in 2050. Hayama
11. European Commission (2018): A Clean Planet for all - A European strategic long-term vision for a prosperous, modern, competitive and climate neutral economy. Brussels
12. Mobility 4EU (2016): D2.1 – Societal needs and requirements for future transportation and mobility as well as opportunities and challenges of current solutions.

- **Acknowledgement**

The project leading to this application has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 807087.

- **Disclaimer**

The results/conclusions of this paper reflect only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

